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The Effect of Work Discipline and Work Environment on the Performance of AL Hudori Cooperative of Palembang Employees

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine the effect of work discipline on employees performance; the effect of work environment on employees performance; the variable that has the most dominant effect on employees performance; and the effect of work discipline and work environment simultaneously on performance employees. The population of this research is employees of AL Hudori Cooperative Palembang with the total 91 respondents taken using the sensus method and this research used multiple linear regression. The result of it showed that: 1.) The effect of work discipline have a significant effect on employees performance of AL Hudori Cooperative Palembang; 2.) Work environment has a significant effect on employees performance of AL Hudori Cooperative Palembang; 3.) Work environment variable has the most dominant effect on employees performance of AL Hudori Cooperative Palembang; 4.) Work discipline and work environment simultaneously have a significant effect on employees performance of AL Hudori Cooperative Palembang. The suggestion that can be given to the company is expected to be able to improve employees discipline such as understanding assignments, being quick to do assignments, wisely utilizing office facilities, and expected to prioritize the improvement of employees' environmental conditions so that employees performance increases.

Keywords: Work discipline, Work Environment, Employees Performance

1. Introduction

Human resource is the actor of the whole planning up to the evaluation which can utilize other resources owned by a particular organization. Because human resource is the most valuable and most important asset in an organization, the success of an organization depends much on the human element (Nawawi, 2005).

Employee performance is the output or achievement of work in quality and quantity which is achieved by employees. Simamora (2008) defines the performance as the level of work achievement which forms the employee's job. According to Gibson et al. in Srimulyo (1999), there are three factors affecting performance: 1) individual factors consisting of competence (ability or skills: mental or physical), background (family, social level,

work experience, and payroll), and demography of someone; 2) psychological factors consisting of perception, role, study, attitude, personality, motivation, and work satisfaction; and 3) organizational factors consisting of organization structure, work design, leadership, and compensation (award system).

Employees with high discipline will do the work although they are not being monitored by their seniors. Moreover, they will not corrupt the working hours to do other things which do not relate to the work. Besides, they will also obey the applied rules in their work environment with high awareness without any coercion. Therefore, discipline has a strong impact on an organization to succeed in achieving the planned goals.

Suradinata (2007) states that discipline is a condition created and formed through the process of behavior, learning, obedience, loyalty, and respect to the regulations and norms applied. If the values of discipline have been embedded in the employee, behavior or attitude done will not be burdensome; instead, it will be a custom which will be burdensome when it is not done. The process, attitude, and behavior in the discipline are formed through the training of family, education, and experiences or impacts from the exemplary in life around its surroundings. If the work discipline is well- embedded, they will be aware of norms or company's rules and the demand of the obedience on norms or the rules (Hasibuan, 2007).

In giving work and responsibility to employees, the leaders of the company should consider their work environment. The work environment is a condition which relates to the physical condition of the workplace which can affect psychological changes, such as boredom, monotonous work, and tiredness (Schultz and Schultz, 2010). Work environment, according to Robbinson (2009), institutions or extrinsic strengths which potentially influence the organization's performance. The public environment, in this case, is classified into two, i.e., general environment and specific environment. The general environment is anything outside the organization which potentially influences the organization which can be in the form of the social or technological condition. The specific environment is anything in the environment which can influence individual or a group indirectly and directly in doing their activities.

Employee performance is the achievement of the employees in carrying out their work. Mathis and Jackson (2010) standardize someone's performance from the quantity of output, quality of output, output period, the presence in the workplace, and cooperative behavior. Those standards are determined from the criteria of work, such as explaining any information given by the organization to be done by the employees. Therefore, individual performance in working criteria can also increase employee performance. In this context, discipline becomes the key to realize the company's goals. The employees with good discipline will be aware and ready to do their works well (Hasibuan, 2012). It shows that work discipline is very important for a company which influences employee performance.

Al Hudori Cooperative is a cooperative for savings and loans. The success of the cooperation is very supported by employee performance. One of the important things relating to the employee work in doing effective works is the work environment. Therefore, the work environment, in this case, is the factor which is required to be concerned by the company because it closely relates to the low and high spirit of the employees. If a particular work environment of a company is conducive, it can encourage a high spirit of working which then influences the employee performance.

In accordance with the aforementioned statement, Al Hudori Cooperative should have employees with good performance. Good performance can be seen from the level of work discipline which is owned by each employee. However, the number of the employees who were absent in April, May, and December are high. On April and May, the number of absent employees was 18.7% and 19.8% in December which is the highest one. One of the reasons why they were absent is that they are applying for another job. Meanwhile, some were absent without any information. In this case, it indicates that the level of discipline of the employees is still low. Then, the absence of strict punishment from the cooperation becomes another the cause of the employee absence without information because they thought it was acceptable. The employee's absence means that they have decreased their working hours to finish work set by the deadline. Besides, the high number of absence shows that there is a problem on the employee work discipline in Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang which can affect the employee performance.

However, there are some research gaps found in relation to this topic; one of which is on the study by Khasifah and Nugrahaeni (2016) observing the effect of work discipline, workload, and work environment on the performance of the Balai Besar employees. In their study, they investigated the work environment in physical

aspects, while this study investigates the work environment in physical and nonphysical aspects. The result of the study finally shows that work discipline positively and significantly affects the employee performance. Besides, work environment positively and significantly affects the employee performance.

In achieving the goals, the employees of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang are very influenced by the system of discipline and work environment in order to increase employee performance. However, one of the challenges appearing is the failure of achieving optimal employee performance in accordance with the applied work standards.

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Design

The causal research design is used to know the causal variable (independent variable) and the variable that becomes the result (dependent variable) which is aimed to know the correlation and dependence among the variables and to know the effect of the causal variable (independent variable) on the dependent variable. The research design is used to prove the hypotheses that have been set. In this study, there are three variables, i.e., discipline (X_1), work environment (X_2), and a dependent variable named employee performance (Y). Moreover, multiple linear regression method is used to know the effect of discipline and work environment on the employee of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang.

2.2 Population and Sample

The population of this study is 91 employees of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang which were chosen using the census method.

2.3 Analysis Method

2.3.1 Item Validity Test

Validity test is used to measure the validity of an indicator in the form of a questionnaire. The purpose of having validity test is to show the extent to which a measuring instrument is able to measure what to measure. The test tool used to measure intercorrelation level among variables and the possibility of conducting factor analysis is Kaiser Meyer Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO). The values of KMO vary from 0 to 1. In this case, the expected value should be $> .5$ so that analysis factor can be conducted (Ghozali, 2009). Loading factor will be valid if the value is $> .4$ meaning that the indicator has been valid. On the other hand, the invalid items will be eliminated and excluded from the next analysis. Furthermore, the valid items will be processed in the reliability test.

2.3.2 Reliability Test

The reliability test is aimed to show to what extent the measurement is conducted without any mistakes and to guarantee the consistent measurement. If a measurement used twice shows similar symptoms, and the result of measurement is relatively consistent, the measuring tool is reliable. The instrument will be valid if the value of Cronbach Alpha is more than $.6$ (Kuncoro, 2009).

2.3.3 Classical Assumption

In order to avoid the deviation of the result of the regression analysis, the classical assumption test needs to be conducted. The classical assumption test consists of a normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test.

2.4 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

2.4.1 Multiple Regression Equation

The data will be statistically processed using Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) version 23.0 for windows. Multiple linear regression analysis is an analysis used to know the regression equation showing the equation between the dependent variable and independent variable and to know the regression coefficients and their significance, so they can be used to answer the hypotheses. The equation of multiple regression is formulated as follow:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e \quad (1)$$

Note:

Y= Employee Performance

X₁= Work Discipline

X₂= Work Environment

a= regression constant

b₁=regression coefficient of work discipline

b₂= regression coefficient of work environment

e= error

2.4.2 Correlation (r) and Determinant Coefficient (R²)

Correlation analysis is used to determine the correlation between variables. The type of Spearman correlation technique is used in this study because the data is ordinal data (levelled data). Spearman correlation technique is used to analyze the correlation between work discipline and employee performance variables and analyze the correlation between work environment and employee performance variables. Through the correlation test, the magnitude or strength of the correlation and the direction of the relationship or correlation of the two variables can be determined.

The correlation between variables is expressed in the correlation coefficient. The correlation coefficient interprets the strength of the correlation. The magnitude of the correlation coefficient is between +1 to -1. The magnitude of the correlation coefficient indicates the strength of the correlation between variables. The criteria for the correlation strength according to Sugiyono (2016) are as follows:

- a. 0.000 - 0.199 = Very low
- b. 0.200 - 0.399 = Low
- c. 0.400 - 0.599 = Medium
- d. 0.600 - 0.799 = High
- e. 0.800 - 1,000 = Very high

Negative and positive signs in the correlation coefficient indicate the direction of the correlation between two variables. If the correlation coefficient is negative, the correlation between the two variables is inversely proportional. On the other hand, if the correlation coefficient is positive, the correlation between the two variables is directly proportional. To determine how far the independent variable can explain the dependent variable, the determination value needs to be known by determining R² determinant because it consists of absolute ratio and comparison values. The usefulness of adjusted R² is:

1. As the measure of the accuracy of a regression line applied to a group of survey data. The greater the value of R², the more precise the regression line will be. On the other hand, the smaller the adjusted R² will be the more incorrect the regression line represents the observation data.
2. To measure the proportion or percentage of the number of variations of the dependent variable, it must measure the contribution of the independent variable to the dependent variable.

2.5 Hypothesis Test Technique

2.5.1 T-Test (Partial)

Statistic hypothesis t-test is conducted to know if individually there is the effect on each independent variable toward the dependent variable. The test for every coefficient of the independent variable is conducted using 5% of t value of the level of significance (Gujarati, 1995). Each coefficient of the independent variable will be significant if the absolute value of t_{calculate} is ≥ t_{table} of probability value which level of significance is smaller than .05 (the level of confidence chosen). The conclusion of the hypothesis can be conducted in two ways.

Based on the comparison of t value:

- a. If t_{calculate} < t_{table}, H_a is rejected. It means that there is no effect of the independent variable on dependent variable.
- b. If t_{calculate} ≥ t_{table}, H_a is accepted. It means that there is an effect of independent variable on dependent variable.

Based on the comparison of significant value,

- a. If the value of sig. > .05, H_a is rejected. It means that there is no effect of independent on dependent variable.

b. If the value of $\text{sig.} \leq .05$, H_a is accepted. It means that there is effect of independent on dependent variable.

2.5.2 F-Test (Simultaneous)

F-test is conducted to test independent variable and dependent variable simultaneously with 5% level of significant (Gujarati, 1995).

- If the significance is $\leq .05$, H_0 is rejected, but H_a is accepted. It means that there is significant effect of independent variable simultaneously on the dependent variable.
- If the level of significance is $> .05$, H_0 is accepted, but H_a is rejected. It means that there is no significant effect of independent variable simultaneously on dependent variable.

3. Findings

3.1 Validity and Reliability Test

The validity test in this study uses Pearson correlation (Product Moment). A high validity item will occur when the item has high correlation on the score total item. The validity test of this study uses the Correlation Pearson Product Moment test with the level of significance is .5 (5% error). The significance test is conducted by comparing r calculate and r critical and based on the level of sig. If r calculate $\geq .3$ (r critical) and the value of sig. (2-tailed) is less than .05, the result is valid (Kuncoro, 2009). The result of the validity test toward the variable of work discipline, work environment, and employee performance are explained in Appendix.

The result of the validity test on discipline variable shows that all question items on the discipline variable have greater r calculate than r critical (.300). Therefore, it can be concluded that all question items on discipline variable are valid. The result of the validity test on work environment variable shows that all question items on work environment variable have greater r calculate than r critical (.300). Therefore, it can be concluded that all items on the work environment variable are valid. The result of the validity test on employee performance variable shows that the items of the variable have greater r calculate than r critical (.300). Therefore, it can be concluded that all question items on the variable are valid.

Reliability test is used to show the extent to which the measurement conducted without any mistakes and can guarantee the consistency of measurement. If a measurement is used to measure similar symptom and the result of the measurement is relatively consistent, the measurement is reliable. An instrument is reliable when the value of Cronbach Alpha is more than .6 (Kuncoro, 2009). The result of the reliability test can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. The Result of Reliability Test

Variable	Statement Item	Cronbach alpha	Description
Work discipline	8	.930	Reliable
Work environment	6	.964	Reliable
Employee performance	8	.631	Reliable

Source: Processed primary data (2018)

The result of the reliability test shows that the value of Cronbach Alpha of the variables used in this study is more than .60. It means that all variables of this study are reliable.

3.2 Classical Assumption Test

In this study, multiple linear regression analysis is used. Therefore, the classical assumption test as the requirement test needs to be conducted. The result of the classical assumption test is described as follow:

3.2.1 Normality Test

Normality test is aimed to test whether the data has a normal distribution. If this assumption is neglected, the statistical test will be invalid. The result of the normality test using Kolmogrov-Sminov is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The Result of Normality Test

Variable	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Work discipline	.052
Work environment	.063
Employee performance	.077

Source: Processed primary data (2018)

Since the criterion of the test is on the .05 level of significance, the data is called normal when it has Asymp. Sig.(2-tailed) > .05. The result of statistical Kolmogrov-Sminiv test shows that all variables have Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) > .05. In short, all variables used in this study have a normal distribution.

3.2.2 Heteroscedasticity Test

The purpose of having heteroscedasticity is to test the similarity of variants of residual from one observation to another. If the residual has a similar variety, Homoscedasticity occurs. On the other hand, if the variety is different, heteroscedasticity occurs. The result of heteroscedasticity test is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The Result of Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Sig.
Discipline toward employee performance	.149
Work environment toward employee performance	.285

Source: Processed primary data (2018)

From the heteroscedasticity test, it is found that the value of sig. is > .05 for all correlations between the independent and dependent variable. Therefore, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur in the data of this study.

3.2.3 Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is conducted to test whether there is a correlation among the dependent variables on model regression. In this case, a good regression model will occur if multicollinearity is not detected. The result of multicollinearity test is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. The Result of Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Work discipline	1,000	1,000
Work environment	1,000	1,000
Employee performance	1,000	1,000

Multicollinearity is detected using the value of tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF). Multicollinearity occurs when the value of tolerance is lower than .10, or the value of VIF is more than 10 (Ghozali, 2016). The result of multicollinearity test shows that the value of all variables is more than .1 and the value of VIF is less than 10. Thus, it shows that multicollinearity does not occur in all regression models of this study.

3.2.3 Multiple Linear Regression Test

The completion of a simple linear regression model is conducted using SPSS program version 23.0. The simple linear regression model analysis is used in this study because it can test the significance and the extent to which the relationship between the independent and dependent variable.

Table 5 The Result of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.
Constant	12.954	2.188	5.920	.000
Work discipline	.314	.064	4.895	.000
Work Environment	.347	.074	4.712	.000

Based on the result of linear regression analysis, the value of the constant is 12.954, the regression coefficient of discipline variable is .314, and the coefficient of regression of work environment is .347. Therefore, the regression equation can be formulated as follow:

$$KK = 12.954 + .314DK + .347LK$$

Note:

DK = work discipline

LK = work environment

KK = employee's performance

Based on the coefficient of regression or each variable, the relationship between discipline and work environment toward employee performance can be described as follow:

1. Constant indicated by 12.954 shows that when the value of work discipline and work environment is zero, the value of employee performance is 12.954.
2. The regression coefficient of work discipline variable toward employee performance is positive (.314). It means that the direction of work discipline variable and employee performance relationship is in the same direction. Every time the unit of work discipline goes up one level, the increase of employee performance will be .314.
3. The regression coefficient of work environment variable toward employee performance is positive (.347). It means that the direction of the work environment variable and employee performance relationship is in the same direction. Every time the unit of work environment goes up one level, the increase of employee performance will be .347.
4. The regression coefficient of the work environment which is .347 shows greater value than the regression coefficient of work discipline which is .314. The result shows that the work environment affects more dominantly on the employee performance than work discipline. As a result, the hypothesis 3 is rejected.

3.3 The Result of Correlation Analysis between Variable and Determinant Coefficient

The analysis of correlation in this study is conducted to test the relationship between the independent and dependent variable. The direction and strength of both variables are observed based on r value. The result of the correlation test can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. The Result of Correlation Analysis and Determinant Coefficient

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.585	.342	.327	3.82213

Based on Table 5, the value of R is .585 indicating positive sign can be categorized into moderate. It is in line with Sugiyono's (2016) statement that the criterion of relationship strength among variables is .400-.599 which is categorized into moderate. It means that the work discipline and work environment correlate positively and moderately toward employee performance. For the adjusted R square test, it is used to know the extent to which the independent variable can explain the dependent variable. Based on Table 4.14, the value of adjusted R square is .342 which means that the work discipline variable and employee performance can explain that the employee performance is 34.2% and the rest is 65.8% which is explained by other variables which are not observed in this study, such as training, leadership types, incentive, and motivation.

3.4 Hypothesis Test

3.4.1 The Result of T-Test

T-test is used to know the significance of the effect of each independent and dependent variable. If the value of sig. is $< .05$ and the value of t calculate $\geq t$ table, H_0 is rejected. It means that there is a significant effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Based on t-test, the significant effect of independent on the dependent variable in each hypothesis can be seen as follow.

Table 6 Table of Level of Significance

Model	t	Sig
Work discipline (X_1)	4.895	.000
Work Environment (X_2)	4.712	.000

Hypothesis 1: The effect of work discipline on employees performance

The value of t table of one-tailed on df is 89, and the 95% of confidence level is 1.662. The effect of work discipline variable on employees performance shows that the value of sig. is $.000 < .05$ and the value of t calculate is $4.895 > t$ table (1.662). It means that H_0 is rejected, but H_1 is accepted. Thereby, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of work discipline on employee performance causing hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: The effect of the work environment on employees performance

The value of t table of one-tailed on df is 89, and the 95% of confidence level is 1.662. The effect of work environment variable on employees performance shows that the value of sig. is $.000 < .05$ and the value of t calculate is $4.712 > t$ table (1.662). It means that H_0 is rejected, but H_1 is accepted. Thereby, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of the work environment on employee performance causing hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Work discipline variable has the most dominant effect on the employees' performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang.

The result of multiple linear regression analysis in Table 4.13 shows that the regression coefficient of the work environment variable is greater than the regression coefficient of work discipline with the regression coefficient of work environment is .347, and the regression coefficient of work discipline is .314. Therefore, it shows that the work environment variable more dominantly affects employee performance than work discipline. As a result, hypothesis 3 which states that the work discipline variable has a dominant effect is rejected.

3.4.2 The Result of F-Test

F-test is used to now the significance of independent variable simultaneously on the dependent variable. If the value of sig. is $< .05$ and F calculate $\geq F$ table, H_0 is rejected. It means that there is significant effect simultaneously between the independent variable and dependent variable. The result of F-test is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. The Result of F-Test

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	669.162	2	334.581	22.903	.000 ^b
Residual	1285.563	88	14.609		
Total	1954.725	90			

a. Dependent Variable: KK

b. Predictors: (Constant), LK, DK

Source: Processed Primary Data (2018)

Hypothesis 4: Work discipline and work environment simultaneously affect employees performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang mostly.

Regarding on F-test, the value of F table on df is 2.88, and the 95% of confidence level is 3.10. The value of sig. is $.000 < .05$ and the value of F calculate is $24.396 > F$ table (3.10). It means that H_0 is rejected, but H_1 is accepted. Then, it is stated that there is a significant effect of work discipline simultaneously on work environment on employee performance. As a result, hypothesis 4 stating that work discipline and work environment simultaneously affect employees performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang mostly.

4. Discussion

4.1 *The Effect Of Discipline On Employee Performance*

Hypothesis 1 stating that work discipline affects the performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang employees significantly is **accepted**. The result shows that well-disciplined employees, according to Ardiansyah and Wasilati (2014), have followed the procedure of work arranged by the company which can affect their work performance. High obedience in following the company rules can also increase the employee self-confidence, so their performance increases. Moreover, well-disciplined employees will create employee's self-control, do the work in order, and have self-determination in working which increases the performance (Simamora, 2008). The similar statement is also stated by Hasibuan (2007) that employees will be aware of norms or company rules and demand of obedience on norms or the rules if work discipline is well-embedded.

In this case, work discipline takes an important role in running the daily activities of employees. Employees with high discipline will work well even without the seniors' monitor. Moreover, they will obey rules in the work environment with high awareness without any coercion. Those who have high discipline will have good performance if it is compared to those who are lazy because they will use working hours based on the target set.

The implementation of discipline in a company is aimed to make all employees obey every applied rule without any coercion. Good discipline can be seen from the high awareness of employees in obeying every applied rule and the high responsibility of their own employees. In the performance context, discipline will create mental readiness to do work. It is likely to realize more optimal performance (Hasibuan, 2007).

The result of this study is in line with the study conducted by Khasifah and Nugraheni (2016), Yoga Arsyenda (2013), Septiasari (2017), Primananda and Djastuti (2015: 1-11), Jeffrey and Soleman (2017), Hamlan Daly (2015) which show that work discipline affects employee performance significantly and positively. In addition, Lastriani (2014) states that better discipline is better employee performance is.

The result of the descriptive analysis shows that most employees of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang do their work on time, go home based on applied working hours, and obey the rules and seniors. In this study, employees' good discipline is based on the punctuality aspects in doing work, presence and obedience in obeying rules which increase the employee performance by being able to do work based on leader's instruction, the ability to do right work, the ability to work based on the work target, the ability to finish work on time, punctual presence, the ability to have good relationship with other colleagues, and the ability to do cooperative work well with other colleagues. However, there are some employees who were absent without any information. Based on the work discipline variable, the answers which have the highest percentage is "agree" and "strongly agree" which indicator is the punctuality of the employees in doing their work. It is presented by 47 employees (51.6%).

Regarding the result, it shows that most employees have been disciplined in working by doing the work on time. The more disciplined the employees in doing their work on time is the better the performance is. Those who can do their work on time have good quality because the work is done correctly. In this case, if the employees can do their work based on the deadline, the work will not pile up. In this condition, the employees can give a good result on the work they do. Moreover, they can do the work correctly.

4.2 *The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance*

Hypothesis 2 stating that the work environment significantly affects the performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang employees is **accepted**. Carnevale (1992) states that the physical environment can support productivity and quality more only if greater voice and control on design and physical environment operational are given to

line manager and employees. Besides, the physical condition of work can influence productivity. According to Sedarmayanti (2011), the impact of work environment suitability can be seen in a long term, while worse work environment can demand more energy and time and cannot support efficient planning work system. Therefore, the work environment is a condition which relates to the physical condition of the workplace and influences the behavior and attitude of the employees. It is said so because the physical condition of the workplace can influence the psychological changes, such as boredom, monotonous work, and tiredness (Schultz and Schultz, 2010).

In the context of the work environment, work environment consists of some aspects, such as appropriate room layout, good room lighting, and cold temperature which can increase employee work efficiency. If the condition of the environment can be fulfilled, work environment which is conducive will occur and can positively affect the employee performance (Robbins, 2009: 86). Moreover, a good work environment will give personal comfort and increase the spirit of working of the employees; thus, they can do their work well. Besides, they will be happier and more comfortable to work if the facilities are clean, not noisy, well-converted air, and sufficient and modern devices. In short, good work environment will affect employee performance.

The result of this study is supported by some studies conducted by Manggiasih and Sunardi (2014), Indarti and Mahda (2014), Khasifah and Nugrahaeni (2016), Samson et al. (2015) which results show that work environment significantly and positively affects employee performance. In addition, Rumengan and Mekel (2015) states that physical and non-physical work environment positively and significantly affect employee performance. Muhammad et al. (2016) in his study also states that the work environment is the encouragement of activating employees to do particular work.

The result of this study also shows that most employees of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang assume that the room lighting and room temperature do not distract their work and the office layout has been in a well-ordered. Because of the condition, the employees can do their work in accordance with the leader direction, do right work, do work based on target, finish the work on time, and cooperate with their colleagues well although some employees present without any information. The answers having the highest percentage is "disagree" and "very disagree" which indicator is about the room layout which is not in order. It is chosen by 40 employees (44%).

Regarding the result, it is found that a good work environment makes the employees work well. The more comfortable the physical environment of the workplace is the more higher the employee performance. The comfortable physical environment condition, especially which relates to room layout which is in order, makes the employees cooperate well with their colleagues and seniors. The reasons are that the work environment, especially good room layout which can keep the work privation of individual work can build good cooperation relationship in working. Moreover, a comfortable work environment makes employees have good emotion, so they can work better.

4.3 Work discipline Variable has the Dominant Effect

Hypothesis 3 stating that work discipline has a dominant effect on the employees of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang is **rejected**. In fact, work environment consisting of many aspects, such as appropriate room layout, good room lighting, and cool temperature can increase employee work efficiency. If the environmental condition can be fulfilled, the work environment which is conducive will be created; thus, it can positively affect employee performance (Robbins, 2009). Besides, a good work environment will give personal comfort and encourage the spirit of the employees, so they can work well. Moreover, the employees will be happier and more comfortable while working if the facilities are clean, not noisy, well-converted air, and sufficient and modern devices. In short, good work environment will affect their performance.

On the other hand, good work discipline can be seen from the high awareness of the employees in obeying every rule applied and the high responsibility of the individual's work. In relation to performance, work discipline will create mental readiness to do particular work. It is likely to result in performance which is more optimal (Hasibuan, 2007). However, the work environment can increase employee performance more than work discipline because the work environment is a factor which can give them motivation in which motivation causes the desire of the employees to act (Mathis and Jackson, 2012).

The result of this study is supported by a study conducted by Rahmasita (2015) stating that the work environment significantly and more dominant affect employee performance than work discipline. Simultaneously, work

discipline and work environment significantly affect employee performance. It is supported by a study conducted by Maddinsyah and Wahyudi (2017) stating that the work environment has a greater effect on employee performance than work discipline.

Based on the work environment context, the answers having the highest percentage are "disagree" and "strongly disagree" which indicator is about the room layout which is not in order. The answers are chosen by 40 employees (44%). The highest correlation between the physical work environment and cooperative behavior of employee performance variable is considered as moderate. Based on the work discipline context, the answers having the highest percentage are "agree" and "strongly agree" which indicator is about the punctuality of employees in doing their work. The answers are chosen by 47 employees (51.6%).

The result shows that the working room which is in order can create good employee emotion, so they can work better. The employees can cooperate better with other employees and show better performance. Moreover, a good emotional condition can support employee performance more than their awareness to work based on the deadline because the condition of the work environment can be a motivation to work better.

4.4 The Effect of Work discipline and Environment Simultaneous on the Employee Performance

Hypothesis 4 stating that work discipline and work environment simultaneously affect the performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang employees is **accepted**.

The condition of the workplace can affect psychological changes, such as work boredom, monotonous work, and tiredness (Schultz and Schultz, 2010: 45). Good work environment will give personal comfort and encourage employee spirit or working; thus, they can do their job well. Besides, they will be happier and more comfortable in working if the available facilities are clean, not noisy, well-circulated air, sufficient and modern. As a result, it affects employee performance.

Hasibuan (2007) states that if work discipline is well-embedded, the employees will be aware of norms or company's rules and the demand of obedience on the norms and the rules. In other words, work discipline holds an important role in doing daily activities of the employees. The employee with high discipline will work well although they are not supervised by seniors. Moreover, they will obey the rules which are available within the work environment with high awareness without any coercion.

The result of this study is in line with the study conducted by Rahmasita (2015) stating that work discipline and work environment simultaneously affect employee performance significantly. A similar result is also stated by Primananda and Djastuti (2015) that work discipline and work environment as well as cultural organization simultaneously affects employee performance significantly. Maddinsyah and Wahyudi (2017) also state in their study that work discipline and work environment simultaneously affects employee performance significantly.

In a work environment context, the answers with the highest percentage are "strongly disagree" and "strongly agree" which indicator is about the working room layout which is not in order. The answers were chosen by 40 employees (44%). Moreover, in work discipline context, the answers with the highest percentage are "agree" and "strongly agree" which indicator is about the punctuality of employees in doing their work. The answers were chosen by 47 employees (51.6%).

The result shows that the working room which is well-ordered can affect the psychological change of employees, so they will not be bored, feel monotone, and tired. Moreover, the behavior of working on time in the group can increase employee performance. In addition, besides having good emotion and motivation in working, they will also have high awareness to obey rules in working which can increase their performance.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that:

1. Work discipline significantly affects the employee performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang.
2. Work environment significantly affects the employee performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang.
3. Work environment dominantly affects the employee performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang compared to work discipline.

4. Work discipline and environment simultaneously affect the employee performance of Al Hudori Cooperative of Palembang significantly.

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